

PRIORITY FOR THE INTRODUCTION OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS IN THE SEWING AND KNITTED INDUSTRY

¹Muminov Kholmurodzhon Dilshodzhon ugli, ²Mirpayzieva Gulnoza Mirgiasovna,
³Nizomov Norkhuzha Bakhodirovich

^{1,2,3}Tashkent State Technical University, assistant of the department "Metrology, technical regulation, standardization and certification"

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Abstract. *This article will consider the priority areas for the implementation of international standards in the clothing and knitwear industry. It is indicated that on the basis of these international standards, it is planned to establish cooperation in the field of production.*

Keywords: *international Standard, assortment, quality, efficiency, knitwear, textiles, knitwear.*

INTRODUCTION

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the accelerated development of the textile and clothing and knitwear industry" dated December 14, 2017 No. UP-5285 identified the main tasks:

1. Raising the technical and technological level
2. Ensuring production efficiency
3. Competitiveness and science intensity of products
4. Export growth
5. Active investment and innovation activity
6. Deepening industry cooperation
7. Formation of market infrastructure

All the tasks presented above take priority in the development of economic growth, the system of standardization and certification, design, innovative technologies, and personnel training[1].

Development priorities:

- ✓ expansion of ICT in the industry management system;
- ✓ improvement of personnel training;
- ✓ development of the system of standardization and certification;
- ✓ improving the image of domestic products, design development;
- ✓ introduction of innovative technologies, know-how;
- ✓ implementation of the cluster development model;
- ✓ increase in the share of the textile industry in GDP;
- ✓ implementation of international standards;

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The sewing and knitting industry is a large branch of light industry that produces a wide range of products and fabrics for both household and technical purposes. The range of knitwear is very wide - these are hosiery, underwear, outerwear, sportswear, swimwear, gloves, technical knitwear for rubber, footwear and other industries, artificial fur, batting, corsets, belts, scarves, medical stockings, blood vessel prostheses and so on.

Knitwear has valuable consumer qualities - elasticity, breathability, high hygiene, low wrinkling, good drape, the ability to fit the figure well, and ease of use. Very thin, smooth yarns, often shiny, are relevant. It is these qualities of knitted fabric and knitted products that allow us to accept international standards. International standards - this is the creation at the international level of a unified methodological basis for the development of new and improvement of existing quality systems and their certification [3,4].

RESULTS

Goals of international standardization:

1. convergence of the quality level of products manufactured in different countries;
2. ensuring the interchangeability of elements of complex products;
3. promotion of international trade;
4. promotion of mutual exchange of scientific and technical information and acceleration of scientific and technological progress.
5. establishing requirements for the technical level and quality of products, raw materials, semi-finished products and components, as well as norms, requirements and methods in the field of design and production of products, allowing to accelerate the introduction of advanced methods for the production of high quality products and eliminate the irrational variety of types, brands and sizes ;
6. the development of unification and aggregation of industrial products as the most important condition for the specialization of production; integrated mechanization and automation of production processes, increasing the level of interchangeability, efficiency of operation and repair of products;
7. ensuring the unity and reliability of measurements in the country, the creation and improvement of state standards of units of physical quantities, as well as methods and means of measurement of the highest accuracy;
8. development of unified systems of documentation, systems of classification and coding of technical and economic information;
9. adoption of uniform terms and designations in the most important areas of science, technology, sectors of the economy;
10. formation of a system of labor safety standards, systems of standards in the field of nature protection and improvement of the use of natural resources;
11. creation of favorable conditions for foreign trade, cultural, scientific and technical ties.

Taking into account the requirements of the global market for textile products and in order to expand the geography of exports, the enterprises have begun work on obtaining such certificates as BCI, BSCI, OEKO-TEX Standard 100, SEDEX, GOTS.

STANDARD 100 near OEKO-TEX is an independent international certification system for textile products at all stages of production (from raw materials to the finished product), which consists in checking products for the presence of harmful substances [5].

BSCI is an initiative developed by a non-profit organization, the Foreign Trade Association (FTA), based in Brussels. The goal of BSCI is to initiate sustainable improvement in the performance of supplier countries through the introduction of social responsibility monitoring in global trade.

The Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS) is an internationally recognized standard. GOTS guarantees the organic status of textiles, from the collection of raw materials and environmentally and socially responsible production to the finished product, in order to provide reliable guarantees to consumers.

The ECO Textile Organic Textile Standard (ECOMark) is the world's leading standard for the processing of textiles made from organic fibers. It defines high-level environmental criteria throughout the organic textile supply chain and requires social criteria to be met.

In Uzbekistan, the process of harmonization of national standards for textile and clothing products with international standards is in full swing. Favorable conditions are being created for exporting companies to certify products and expand cooperation with international organizations. Work is also underway to open offices of foreign demanded certification bodies, such as Sedex and BSCI.

Currently, international standards and certificates such as ISO 9001:2015 have been implemented in 1100 enterprises, 45 - OEKO-TEX, 12 - BSCI, 6 - GOTS, 7 - SEDEX.

JV "UZTEX GROUP" LLC is the first and only textile company in the CIS countries, which not only passed the BSCI - Business Social Compliance Initiative certification, but also received the highest absolute category "A" in all 13 principles and codes of this International Standard. European standards OEKO-Tex and Sedex for textile and knitted products have been implemented at 21 enterprises. Thanks to this, in particular, the Samo Textile company in the Andijan region supplied products worth \$5 million to European markets. Bukhara Cotton Textile also exported \$5 million worth of goods to the US, UK, Turkey and Germany. In 2019, the volume of exports of textile products from Uzbekistan amounted to \$1.9 billion. It is expected that by 2025 this figure will grow to \$7 billion [4].

DISCUSSION

Work in this direction continues. By the end of the year, the modernization of 14 laboratories specializing in food, metallurgical and light industry products will be completed. More than 1300 textile industry enterprises work according to international quality standards. This figure is expected to reach 1650 in 2023.

Fig.1.

Source: State Statistics Committee, UzTekstilProm, RB Asia and UOIK

According to the schedule, there is a steady growth dynamics, which is the result of an active state policy of import substitution by stimulating the export potential of enterprises.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4453 “On measures to further develop the light industry and stimulate the production of finished products” dated September 16, 2019 is expected to increase exports to about 4 billion US dollars. by 2023[2]. In order to increase international trade turnover, implement the signed intergovernmental agreements and agreements reached during the state visits of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev Sh. , China, the Republic of Korea, Russia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, etc.

Growing priority for the development of textile production in the future

Table 1

2025	2030	2035
Partnership agreements with international fashion and design agencies	The use of new generation sewing machines to automate the technological part of production	Ensuring the export of high-quality products with a single label "Uztextile"
Upgrading production technologies in the textile industry	Implementation of technologies for the production of "smart clothes" with constant access to the Internet, measuring health indicators, etc.	The introduction of nanotechnology in the textile industry
Adoption of international quality standards, eradication of the problem of labor slavery	Improving the efficiency of filter nonwovens to solve the environmental problems of large industrial enterprises	Optimization of the number of personnel and their professional qualification structure
Creation of a modern educational and research textile technopark	Segmentation of promising new product markets, expansion and diversification of product sales markets (Asia, Africa, America). Development of marketing and advertising of products, image advertising and PR events	Solving the problem of providing jobs for workers in the textile industry reduced during automation and robotization (75% of workers are women)
Preservation and development of existing related segments of the industry, including building a technological chain for the production of leather materials (from raw hides to finished leather for the clothing, footwear, furniture and automotive industries)		
Training of qualified technical personnel for the textile industry		

CONCLUSION

- The textile industry begins to develop rapidly
- The country receives a large amount of foreign investment
- Promotion of domestic brands and finished products will be able to both satisfy domestic needs and export in large volumes
- The introduction of international standards ensures the growth of exports.

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